

Cryptocurrency-Based Mobile Payments with Near-Field Communication-Enabled Devices

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Abstract—Cryptocurrencies are getting increasingly popular, but very few of them can be conveniently used in daily mobile phone purchases. To solve this problem, we demonstrate how to build a functional prototype of a mobile cryptocurrency-based e-commerce application that communicates with Near-Field Communication (NFC) tags. Using the system, users are able to purchase physical items with an NFC tag that contains an e-commerce URL. The payment is done simply by touching the tag with a mobile device and accepting the payment. Our method is constructive: we describe the design and technologies used in the implementation and evaluate the security and performance of the solution. Our main finding is that the analysis and measurements show that our solution is feasible for e-commerce.

Keywords—Cryptocurrency, e-commerce, NFC, mobile devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

CRYPTOCURRENCIES like Bitcoin [1] have been the focus of both technical and economical discussion in the 2010s. It has been estimated that, in 2017, people used \$190.2 million worth of Bitcoin monthly on merchant services [2]. Yet, this is a minor amount compared with estimated \$1.35 trillion spent using mobile wallets during the same year [3]. With a few exceptions like GraftCoin [4], we lack a method of making a payment with an NFC-enabled¹ mobile device as with ApplePay [5]. The aim of this paper is to provide a simple but working prototype that integrates a cryptocurrency, an NFC reader, and web-based payments.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we explain the basic concepts of cryptocurrency, NFC, and a web interface with a cryptocurrency wallet. Section III describes our implementation in more detail. Finally, Section IV contains a summary and conclusions.

II. BASIC CONCEPTS

A cryptocurrency can be loosely defined as a medium of exchange using cryptography to secure the transactions and to control the creation of new units. Cryptocurrencies are decentralized systems; they do not have a central authority like a national bank to supply the currency. Rather, they use cryptography to control transactions, increase the supply, and prevent fraud [6]. Transactions are recorded in a blockchain that is essentially a distributed database of records, or public

ledger of all transactions or digital events that have been executed and shared among participating parties. Each transaction in the public ledger is verified by consensus of a majority of the participants in the system. Once entered, information can never be erased. The blockchain thus contains a certain and verifiable record of every single transaction ever made [7]. The verification process of transactions is called mining. Anyone (with sufficient hardware, software and network resources) can become a miner, and successful verifications are rewarded with cryptocurrency (for details, see [8]).

A transaction record contains the identifiers of the sender, the receiver, and the transaction itself as well as the amount of currency transferred. Since the blockchain contains all the transactions, we could call sender/receiver identifiers simply “wallets” (holders of currency). The balance of a wallet at any time can be computed by traversing the blockchain transactions. In practice, it is more common to use the term “wallet” for a wallet file managed by a program. A wallet program secures the owner’s access to his/her funds by cryptography. Moreover, a wallet program does not store the entire blockchain, rather it downloads the block headers of the blockchain, and the transactions that represent payments to the owner’s identifier [8]. There is no link between a person’s actual identity and his/her wallet(s). With a wallet software available for most popular operating systems, anyone can create a wallet. A cryptocurrency exchange like the now infamous Mt.Gox exchange [6] lets a user convert fiat currency into a cryptocurrency and send it to his/her wallet. Another way of gaining cryptocurrency is mining (since successful verifications are rewarded). Most cryptocurrency wallet programs contain a mining function. An example of a wallet program (UltraNote cryptocurrency) is shown in Fig. 1. The “synchronizing” process shown at the bottom illustrates that the program is loading blockchain headers from the network. The mining button on the right will make the program launch a sub-process that verifies transactions.

Though BitCoin is the best known cryptocurrency, many other similar currencies have been introduced, often in order to remedy weaknesses in BitCoin’s architecture (notably: long transaction times [9]) or intended to a particular group (like Venezuela’s Petro [10]). UltraNote [11] is a cryptocurrency based on Bitcoin, but with an emphasis on privacy. Moreover, the UltraNote platform supports messaging and storing data like documents [11].

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¹ NFC stands for Near-field communication. This contactless communication/data exchange method is standardized in ECMA-340 and ISO/IEC 18092.

Fig. 1 A cryptocurrency (UltraNote) wallet program running on OSX

Near Field Communication (NFC) is a short range (4..10 cm) low-cost, low-energy wireless communication technology jointly developed by Philips and Sony in late 2002 [12]. With an NFC enabled mobile phone, the user first touches a smart object (either an NFC tag, NFC reader, or another NFC enabled mobile phone). After touching, the NFC phone may further make use of received data, or it may use mobile services such as opening a web page or making a web service connection [12]. An NFC tag and a phone application for writing data in the tag are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 (a) An NFC tag

Fig. 2 (b) A phone application for writing data (here just “Hello”) on the tag

NFC tags are inexpensive (currently about \$0.03) but can hold relatively small amounts of information (up to 888 bytes). However, they work without expensive hardware terminals that are required by many other payment schemes (like the Rabbit Card that is popular in Thailand [13]).

After a brief downturn during the “dot com bust” in the early 2000’s, online shopping has enjoyed steady growth [14]. In 2017, users spent \$453.46 billion on the web for retail purchases in the U.S. alone [15]. We loosely define a business-to-consumer based online shopping as a system where a user utilises his or her web browser or mobile application to browse and buy products and services from a seller. Many shop operators use standard e-commerce applications to run their sites [16], among them Magento.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The goal of the design is to provide a method by which users can purchase a physical item by scanning the NFC tag attached to it and paying it with a cryptocurrency. Our solution relies on (i) coding information in the NFC tag as a URL (web address) and (ii) making cryptocurrency wallets available by a web application.

Technically, the only piece of information that needs to be coded in the NFC tag is the address (URL) of a web application with a parameter that identifies the product that carries the tag, like the device (power bank for mobile phones, our product id 10345678) in Fig. 3. However, in our design, the parameter consists of the product id and the seller id. Thus, our database can have a clear distinction of products and sellers (and multiple sellers can sell the same product).

When a mobile device with an NFC reader is brought in contact with the tag, the phone’s NFC application activates a web browser with the URL it reads from the tag. This is shown in Fig. 4 (a) where the web application invoked by the URL authorizes the user, checks his/her balance and if it is sufficient, displays the “Buy” button for the item. Fig. 4 (b)

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